

DIAPHRAGM FORMING OF THERMOSET PREPREG

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SUMMARY:

A mini-autoclave (Pressclave [4]) has been used to form Cycom[®] 977-3 prepreg into a hemispherical cavity. Experiments have been conducted on laminates with variations in thickness and varying temperatures during the forming phase. The effect of forming temperature and diaphragm types on inter- and intraply fibre buckling, deformation of fibre yarns, and diaphragm wrinkling has been investigated. Furthermore, formed samples have been examined for voids and variations in thickness. Both $[0/90]^\circ$ and quasi-isotropic laminates with up to 16 layers have successfully been formed without inter- and intraply fibre buckling, but diaphragm buckling did occur. Diaphragm buckling increased with thinner and less stiff diaphragms. Diaphragm forming formed 977-3 parts did not reveal voids.

KEYWORDS: diaphragm forming, diaphragm wrinkling, interply fibre buckling, intraply fibre buckling, thermoset prepreg, autoclaving.

INTRODUCTION

Autoclaving of thermoset prepregs is a widely used manufacturing technique in the aircraft industry because of the superior material characteristics that can be gained through this process compared to e.g. wet lay-up or vacuum injection. The high temperatures and pressures involved in autoclaving result in high fibre-volume fractions and low void contents. Therefore, autoclaving of thermoset prepregs is considered a high-tech manufacturing technique.

However, high-tech autoclaving mainly depends on the manual mould lay-up of prepreg material. Manual lay-up of high-curvature products is highly complicated and time consuming and therefore part costs are high. Diaphragm forming of thermoset prepregs may be a more cost-efficient process. This technique offers the possibility of lay-up and consolidation of flat prepreg stacks onto a high-curvature mould in a single step. Furthermore, product quality improves as manual lay-up is avoided. In combination with automated tape lay-up, diaphragm forming of thermoset prepreg could offer a significant reduction in part cost compared to conventional techniques [1].

DIAPHRAGM FORMING

Diaphragm forming was originally developed for the processing of composites containing high-temperature thermoplastics like PEI, PPS, and PEEK [2]. The process (see Fig. 1) is based on the principal of placing a flat thermoplastic composite sheet between two thin (50-100 μm) diaphragms of elastic material and clamping this sandwich of diaphragms and thermoplastic composite in between a lower and upper pressure chamber. After heating the laminate to the melting point, it can be formed to the tool geometry by lowering the pressure of the lower pressure chamber. The process is finished by cooling the formed laminate under pressure until the thermoplastic matrix has solidified.

Fig. 1: Diaphragm forming process

Diaphragm forming of thermoset prepreg is similar to that of thermoplastic composites. However, the difference lies in the fact that the thermoset matrix is not melted prior to the forming phase but only heated to decrease the matrix viscosity sufficiently to enable the prepreg to be formed. Furthermore, instead of cooling the laminate immediately after the forming phase has finished, the temperature of the laminate is increased to the matrix's cure temperature after which the matrix undergoes a cure cycle. In essence, the diaphragm forming process for thermoset prepreg is an autoclave curing process in which a single-step forming phase has been incorporated. This single-step forming phase is the strong point of the process; it avoids the time consuming manual lay-up of prepreg onto the production mould prior to an autoclave process. Human input is reduced to preparation of the flat laminate-diaphragm package, and this could be taken over by automated tape lay-up.

Previous research has shown that it is possible to apply the diaphragm forming process to thermoset prepreg; MT6-D (Advanced Composites Group) prepreg had successfully been formed into 3D-elements [3]. This paper describes diaphragm forming-experiments that were conducted on Cycom[®] 977-3 prepreg (Cyttec).

EXPERIMENTAL

Test set-up

Diaphragm forming of the Cycom[®] 977-3 prepreg was conducted in a mini-autoclave called Pressclave. This apparatus has been designed as a mobile unit, which can easily be placed in and out a flat platen press and consists of an autoclave part, pressure valves, control units, a

vacuum pump, and the necessary plumbing. The autoclave part is formed by two hat shaped pressure vessels, which have polished edges for airtight clamping. The lower vessel contains a mould with a hemispherical mould cavity (100mm diameter) (Fig. 2a). The transition from the flat part of the mould into the cavity is slanted. The lower pressure vessel is mobile, while the upper vessel is fastened to the flat platen press. During the diaphragm forming process, the flat platen press presses the two vessels against each other so that an airtight autoclave is created.

Fig. 2: Pressclave test set-up

Band heaters placed around the vessels supply heating. The platens of the press also provide heating, and these are used for cooling. Temperature is monitored by thermocouples located in the lower and upper pressure vessel, in the mould, and in the vacuum ring. Pressure is controlled by pressure sensors in the upper and lower pressure vessels. Nitrogen is used as pressure medium and is supplied from a gas bottle. The hydrostatic pressure difference necessary for the forming process is created by decreasing the pressure in the lower vessel. After the prepreg/diaphragm stack is placed onto the mould, the bottom vessel is moved into the flat platen press, a vacuum is drawn between the diaphragms through the vacuum ring, and the upper and lower vessel are pressurised to the curing pressure (6bar). The sample is heated to the required forming temperature by heating the upper and lower vessels. At the forming temperature, the forming phase is initiated by decreasing pressure in the lower pressure chamber at a constant rate of 1 bar/min. This causes the diaphragms together with the prepreg stack to be pushed into the mould cavity. As soon as the forming phase reaches its end, the prepreg is heated to the curing temperature of 180°C, followed by a one-hour cure at 6bar. Finally, the sample is cooled and removed from the mould.

The build-up of the diaphragm/laminate stack can be seen in Fig. 2. The bottom vessel contains an aluminium mould with a hemispherical cavity (100 mm radius) on which the lower diaphragm is placed (a). Then a vacuum ring is positioned on the bottom vessel (b) and thermocouples are located near the edge of the laminate. A ring of breather material is placed against the vacuum ring to create a proper vacuum between the diaphragms and thereby ensures a proper fixation of the prepreg above the mould cavity. Next step is the positioning of the laminate and placement of strands of carbon fibre running from the breather ring to the edges of the laminate (c). These carbon fibre strands are used for venting air out of the laminate. The final step in the preparation is the positioning of the upper diaphragm (d) after which the whole build-up is moved into the flat platen press.

Materials

The following materials were used for the experiments:

- *Test samples*: CYCOM[®] 977-3 prepreg, with carbon fibre crowfoot satin weave (Cytac); 210x210mm with rounded corners (40mm radius).
- *Diaphragms*:
 - 75µm Capran 988 Nylon film (Aerovac Systems); 470x470mm.
 - 100µm Capran 980 Nylon film (Aerovac Systems); 470x470mm.
 - 100µm Elastomax 1000 Nylon film (Aerovac Systems); 470x470mm.
- *Release agents*: Frekote 44-NC; four layers were applied on the prepreg side of both diaphragms; one layer was also applied on the mould prior to each experiment.
- *Breather material*: Thick glass fibre braid and carbon fibre roving.

RESULTS

The most important criterion for evaluation of the tests, especially for thick samples, was conformity of the part to the mould. Therefore, all samples were visually inspected for complete deformation. In addition, the diaphragms were visually inspected on ruptures. Furthermore, thickness measurements were performed on sixteen-layer samples to determine the effect of the diaphragm forming process on local part thickness. Finally, microscopic pictures were made of sixteen-layer samples for visual inspection on voids.

After the diaphragm forming tests, the following defects and phenomena were observed in the products and diaphragms:

1. Lines of resin on the samples' surface due to wrinkling of the diaphragms.
2. Interply fibre buckling due to a combination of in-plane compression stresses and poor lubrication between fibre layers. As a result, fibres tend to buckle out of plane.
3. Intraply fibre buckling due to exceedance of the maximum shearing angle of a fabric during the deformation process. This type of fibre buckling leads to wrinkles in the fabric.
4. Transverse flow of the fibres (or fibre slipping) due to an applied pressure; the fibres get "squeezed" transverse to the fibre direction.

These phenomena were used in the evaluation of the tests. A distinction was made between "upper" and "bottom" surfaces and diaphragms, where the bottom surface and bottom diaphragm are facing the mould cavity.

0/90° laminates

The first experiments were conducted on two-layered prepreg stacks at temperatures of 50, 70, 90, and 110°C and a forming pressure of 6bar with a forming rate of 1bar/min. The samples were formed with 75µm thick Aerovac Capran 988 diaphragms.

Upper surface

Lower surface

Fig. 3: Diaphragm formed two-layered sample

The six bar forming pressure was sufficient for forming all samples in the temperature range of 50 to 110°C. No signs of interply and intraply fibre buckling were seen on the samples (Fig. 3). However, the upper surfaces of all samples showed lines of resin due to diaphragm wrinkling, mainly on the slanted part (Fig. 4). The number and size of these resin lines increased with increasing forming temperatures from 50 to 90°C. Increasing temperatures reduce the diaphragms' critical buckling stress; the wrinkles in the diaphragms are filled with resin, which afterwards shows as resin lines on the surface. However, at 110°C the resin lines decreased both in size and in number, as the resin flowed out of the diaphragm wrinkles because of the low resin viscosity at 110°C.

On the bottom surface of the samples, indentations were found (Fig. 5). These indentations had formed along lines between adjacent fibres and at locations where fibres interlace. The amount and size of these indentations decreased with increasing temperatures, and were no longer present at 110°C. At lower temperatures, the resin viscosity might be too high for adequate resin flow into the gaps between fibres.

Fig. 4: The effect of diaphragm wrinkling

Fig. 5: Indentations on bottom surface

Fibre slipping was another phenomenon that occurred (fig. 6). Fibres in the corners of the laminate (around the diagonals of the blank) have to shear in order to conform to the deformation of the fabric into the mould. As a result, the fibre angles shift. However, the

fibres between the corners must slip transverse to their longitudinal axis in order to conform to deformation. As a result, transverse fibre slipping had occurred in all samples on the bottom surface, especially where the slanted area changes into the hemispherical part. At this location, the bottom surface fibres are clamped almost immediately at the start of the forming process. As a result, fibres in the hemispherical part have to slip considerably in order to conform to the mould. The fibres on the upper surface however, showed less fibre slippage, as the outer fibre plies can move relative to the inner plies and do not become clamped due to the lubricating effect of the resin. Therefore, fibre slippage can be spread over a larger part of the fibres. The amount of fibre slip did not noticeably change with increasing temperature.

As diaphragm forming of 2-layer samples posed no major problems, the amount of layers was increased to eight. This sample was formed with 75 μ m thick Capran 988 diaphragms at a temperature of 110°C and 6 bar forming pressure (forming rate 1 bar/min). The result was a completely formed sample without any rupture of the diaphragms. However, the lower diaphragm had become so thin on the pole of the part that it was impossible to remove it without tearing. The extreme thin spot in the bottom diaphragm can be explained by the fact that the diaphragm is clamped onto the equator of the mould cavity as soon as forming starts. Hence, all diaphragm deformation had to come from the area above the mould cavity. The upper diaphragm was not clamped and could therefore deform much more uniformly over its area so extreme thin spots were not created. The upper diaphragm could easily be released in one piece.

Fig 6: Fibre slip

Fig. 7: Diaphragm wrinkling in an eight-layer sample

Compared to the deformations and defects in the 2-layer samples there were some differences. The eight-layer samples showed local increase in thickness along the flat and slanted areas. Furthermore, no bottom diaphragm wrinkling had occurred. However, on the upper surface the size of the diaphragm wrinkles had increased compared to those on the two-layer samples. The larger resin lines due to diaphragm wrinkling (Fig. 7) might be explained by the thickness increase on the slanted and flat area of the sample. The thickness of the laminate locally increases due to shearing of the fibres, and such a thickness increase can push the diaphragm in the out of plane direction. In combination with compressive stresses in circumferential direction, this further facilitates diaphragm buckling.

The extreme thinning of the bottom diaphragm might cause premature rupture during the forming of even thicker samples, and this was what happened for the first sixteen-layer sample (forming at 110°C and 6bar (1 bar/min)); the bottom diaphragm had ruptured (Fig. 8). This first sixteen-layer sample showed more upper diaphragm wrinkling than the eight-layer samples. This seems logical as it also showed a more drastic increase in thickness, especially where the fibres shear.

bottom surface

upper surface

Fig. 8: Sixteen-layer sample formed with 75µm diaphragms

bottom surface

upper surface

Fig. 9: Sixteen-layer sample formed with 100µm diaphragms

Fig. 10: Sixteen-layer sample formed with Elastomax 1000 diaphragms

As the appliance of a thicker diaphragm resulted in a decrease of diaphragm wrinkling, the influence of diaphragm stiffness was also investigated. Therefore, a sample was formed with a 100 μ m thick Elastomax 1000 nylon film, which has a lower E-modulus than the Capran 980 film. The laminate was completely deformed (Fig. 10), but it was impossible to release both upper and bottom diaphragms from the finished part, even though the Elastomax diaphragms had been treated with the same release agent as the Capran diaphragms. The sample also showed more and larger wrinkles compared to Capran 980 sample, which is an indication, that diaphragm wrinkling increases with reducing diaphragm stiffness.

Quasi-isotropic laminates

So far, samples containing up to sixteen layers with a (0°, 90°) fibre-orientation had been formed without major problems; no inter- and intraply fibre buckling had occurred, and there was only minor diaphragm buckling. However, forming of quasi-isotropic laminates was expected to be far more difficult as 45°-oriented layers, which have to deform over large distances (along the central axes of the sample) are susceptible to intraply fibre buckling. Therefore, tests were continued with quasi-isotropic stacks. The first attempt was on a sixteen-layer sample with the following orientations: [0/45/45/0/0/45/45/0]_s. As Capran 980 nylon film was temporarily out of stock, the Elastomax 1000 film, despite its poor releasing capabilities, had to be used for the diaphragms. As expected, large parts of the diaphragms could not be removed (Fig. 11). Furthermore, quality of the part was very poor with excessive intraply fibre buckling outward of the upper side of the part. Along the central axes, the 45° layers had had to shear to conform to the mould. However, as more material is pulled into to the cavity along the central axes than from the corners, the 45° layers probably reached their critical shearing angle and started buckling out of plane. The upper diaphragm was not strong/stiff enough to withstand this fibre buckling.

Fig. 11: Quasi-isotropic sample (sixteen layers)

Fig 12: Star-shaped laminate

In order to solve the above mentioned problems with the quasi-isotropic laminates one can look at the blank holders used in the rubber forming process. These blank holders apply tensile forces to the shearing fabric, thereby increasing the maximum shearing angle of the fibres and thus postponing intraply fibre buckling. In case of diaphragm forming, the diaphragms act as a blank holder by means of frictional forces between diaphragms and laminate. This blank holder mechanism will be more effective if the area of laminate outside the mould cavity is increased. This can be done by using a laminate with a star shape; which shape is formed by rotating half of the laminate's layers at a 45° angle (Fig. 12).

The principal of a star-shaped blank was applied to eight- and sixteen-layer samples. Forming temperature was again 110°C with a forming rate of 1bar/min. The first star-shaped sample consisted of eight layers ([45/45/0/0]_s), and was formed at 112°C and one bar/min with Capran 988 diaphragms (75 μ m). The sample (Fig. 13) showed no fibre buckling, and upper

diaphragm wrinkling was comparable to that of eight-layered $[0/90]^\circ$ -samples. Even the sixteen-layered samples ($[45/45/0/0/0/0/45/45/]$ s) had been formed without intraply fibre buckling, but suffered more extensive upper diaphragm wrinkling due to local thickening of the laminate. These tests confirmed that applying a star-shaped instead of a rectangular blank for quasi-isotropic samples, results in less diaphragm wrinkling due to less local thickening of the laminate during forming. Furthermore, intra-ply fibre buckling is prevented this way.

Fig. 13: Samples formed from star-shaped blank

Thickness distributions

Apart from diaphragm wrinkling, the most significant flaw appearing in diaphragm formed samples was that of local thickening of the laminate. This thickening can be contributed to shearing of the fibres. Both the $[0/90]^\circ$ - and the quasi-isotropic samples suffered from local thickening; fig. 14 shows this effect in cross-sections of sixteen-layer samples.

Fig. 14: Thickness distribution in sixteen-layer samples

To get an idea of the amount of thickening, measurements were done on the cross-sections. For the $[0/90]^\circ$ -sample, the thickness of the top half of the sphere was constant at 3.65mm compared to 3.85mm for the quasi-isotropic sample. These values are only 5% and 10% higher than for a flat sixteen-layer laminate, which had had an equal cure cycle as the diaphragm formed samples. The most drastic deviations however, were found around the slanted part of the samples: up to the 50% higher for the $[0/90]^\circ$ sample and up to 35% higher for the quasi-isotropic sample. This shows the enormous effect that fibre shearing has on laminate thickness.

Voids

Based on experience with forming of MT6-D prepreg [3] no breather was used on top of the prepreg during the forming process, as the breather is unable to conform to the shape of the mould without wrinkling. A wrinkling breather causes the prepreg to deform asymmetrically. In order to still be able to evacuate air from the prepreg, carbon fibre rovings were placed at the edges of the prepreg towards the vacuum ring. In order to confirm whether the rovings had been able to sufficiently ventilate air out of the prepreg, the cross-sections of the $[0,90]^\circ$ - and quasi-isotropic sixteen-layer samples were visually inspected for voids. Microscope samples were taken from the slanted area, and from the top of the sphere (Fig. 15 & 16), but no voids were found (the black spots in the pictures are contaminations on the surface). Although the pictures revealed no voids, they showed that a resin-rich layer had formed at the top of the samples (mould-side) (Fig. 16).

Fig. 15: Radius of slanted area $[0,90]$ -sample 2.5x

Fig. 16: resin-rich layer 10x

CONCLUSIONS

Experiments with diaphragm forming of Cycom 977-3 prepreg have proven that this manufacturing process can be applied to thermoset composite parts. The great advantage is that the process offers the possibility of forming a flat prepreg stack into highly curved parts with a high quality. The time-consuming manual lay-up of prepreg on contoured moulds can be avoided, which is particularly advantageous in the case of thick components. Diaphragm forming can be applied to prepreg stacks as thick as sixteen layers.

However, forming thick laminates does require the use of thick and stiff diaphragms; $75\mu\text{m}$ diaphragms can get too thin during the forming process, which can lead to diaphragm rupture and to problems with releasing diaphragms from finished parts. Furthermore, thicker and stiffer diaphragms prevent excessive diaphragm wrinkling.

With respect to product quality, it can be said that diaphragm forming results in parts with a quality very difficult to obtain by hand lay-up. Diaphragm formed parts show good conformity to the mould and do not suffer from intra- and interply fibre buckling. Furthermore, part thickness is constant along less curved areas. Only at high-curvature areas where fibres have to shear to conform to the mould, does considerable part thickening occur. However, this is inherent to the lay-up of fabric on highly contoured moulds, whether this is done by hand or by diaphragm forming. The fact is that forming of contoured parts with diaphragm forming is a matter of minutes compared to hours for hand lay-up.

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